

Assessing at a distance: Formative assessment in Indonesian EFL higher education

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This study is intended to examine the practices of Remote Formative Assessment (RFA) employed by English language lecturers during online teaching sessions. This study used a qualitative case study approach involving 15 lecturers from three state universities located in Aceh Province, Indonesia: Universitas Syiah Kuala, Universitas Islam Negeri Ar-Raniry, and Universitas Samudera. Data were gathered using semi-structured interviews and digital artifact analysis, and the information was examined through thematic analysis. The study identified five prominent practices in the implementation of RFA: (1) adapting assessment activities to digital platforms, (2) providing timely and constructive feedback, (3) monitoring students' learning progress, (4) facilitating collaborative learning, and (5) utilizing multimodal assessment tools. These practices illustrate how lecturers combine numerous digital platforms to maintain formative assessment principles in remote learning. The study highlights the pedagogical implications of RFA for supporting continuous feedback, learner engagement, and adaptive assessment in English language learning in Indonesian higher education.

Keywords: Digital Assessment Tools; English Language Teaching; Higher Education; Online Learning; Remote Formative Assessment

1. Introduction

Digital transformation in higher education has rapidly evolved from a mere tool to a fundamental element of the teaching and learning process. Technology integration has not only changed the way materials are delivered but also revolutionized the entire academic environment, requiring faculty and students to adapt to more flexible, data-driven learning models. This increase enables the interaction, collaboration, and learning activities among the academic community that are no longer limited to physical classrooms. Through learning management systems, video conferencing platforms, and

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various online applications, lecturers and students can engage in teaching and learning processes regardless of time and location. These technological developments have created more flexible learning environments and expanded opportunities for communication and collaboration among learners and instructors. In addition to supporting instructional delivery, digital technology also provides new opportunities for conducting learning assessments, such as offering faster feedback, monitoring student progress, and facilitating interactive learning activities (Bond et al., 2021; Selwyn, 2016). Recent studies also highlight that digital learning ecosystems can support continuous assessment practices and improve learning interactions in higher education environments (Pinto-Llorente & Izquierdo-Álvarez, 2024).

In this context, formative assessment has been widely recognized as an effective approach to support students' learning processes. Formative assessment refers to the process of collecting and interpreting evidence of student learning to inform instructional decisions and support students' learning development (Black & Wiliam, 2009). Unlike summative assessment, which primarily evaluates students' achievement at the end of a learning period, formative assessment focuses on using assessment information to improve learning during the instructional process (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021c). Through continuous feedback, monitoring, and instructional adjustment, formative assessment enables lecturers to identify students' learning needs and provide appropriate support to enhance their learning progress (Heritage, 2010). Research has also demonstrated that formative assessment contributes significantly to improving students' motivation and learning outcomes when implemented consistently in classroom practice (Zhang et al., 2025).

Formative assessment plays an important role in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learning because language development is a gradual process that requires continuous practice, interaction, and feedback. Students need opportunities to recognize their strengths and weaknesses in language use and to improve their performance over time. Previous studies have shown that feedback provided during the learning process helps learners understand the gap between their current performance and expected learning outcomes, thus encouraging them to gradually improve their language proficiency (Panadero et al., 2018; Salmani Nodoushan, 2010; Zhang & Hyland, 2022). In addition, recent research indicates that formative assessment practices (also called interim assessment by Salmani Nodoushan, 2010) can enhance students' motivation and engagement in language learning by promoting autonomy and self-regulated learning strategies (Zhang et al., 2024).

The integration of digital technology into EFL university classrooms has provided a variety of new avenues for practicing language skills, from social

media to collaborative platforms. Technology allows students to be exposed to authentic and interactive language resources that were previously difficult to access in the limited traditional classroom environment. While these technologies offer new opportunities for interaction and feedback, they also require lecturers to reconsider how assessment practices can effectively support students' language development in remote learning environments. Studies in technology-enhanced language learning suggest that digital assessment environments can encourage more interactive learning experiences and provide opportunities for students to engage with feedback more actively (Nicol et al., 2014). However, the effectiveness of such practices depends largely on lecturers' ability to integrate digital tools with pedagogical strategies that support meaningful learning activities.

The growing integration of digital technology in education has also influenced how formative assessment is implemented. Digital platforms allow lecturers to design and implement a variety of assessment activities, including online quizzes, discussion forums, collaborative tasks, and peer assessment. These technologies enable lecturers to collect evidence of student learning more efficiently and provide feedback more promptly in both online and blended learning environments (Bearman et al., 2020). Furthermore, technology-enhanced learning environments can facilitate more interactive and data-informed assessment practices that support students' engagement in the learning process (Spector et al., 2022). Scholars have also suggested that integrating technology into formative assessment can improve the quality of feedback and promote more meaningful learning interactions between lecturers and students (Nicol & Macfarlane-Dick, 2006).

In recent years, the concept of remote formative assessment has gained increasing attention in educational research. Remote formative assessment refers to the implementation of formative assessment practices through digital technologies that enable instructors to monitor students' learning progress and provide feedback in remote or online learning environments (Hill & Barber, 2021). With the rapid development of digital learning environments, researchers have increasingly emphasized the importance of integrating digital tools to support continuous assessment and feedback processes in online language learning contexts (Kang & Lam, 2024). This approach has become particularly relevant as universities continue to adopt technology-mediated learning systems to support online and blended learning.

The importance of remote formative assessment became more evident during the COVID-19 pandemic, when higher education institutions worldwide were required to rapidly transition to online learning environments. This shift accelerated the digital transformation of higher education and encouraged educators to adopt various digital technologies to support teaching, learning,

and assessment practices (Dhawan, 2020). In Indonesia, the pandemic also prompted universities to implement large-scale online learning, leading lecturers to rely heavily on digital platforms such as learning management systems and video conferencing tools to facilitate remote instruction (Rasmitadila et al., 2020). As a result, lecturers needed to adapt not only their teaching strategies but also their assessment practices to ensure that student learning could still be effectively monitored and supported in remote learning contexts.

In the context of Indonesian higher education, the integration of digital technologies has created new opportunities to implement innovative teaching and assessment practices. Several studies have reported that Indonesian lecturers increasingly use digital tools to support student engagement, collaboration, and flexible learning opportunities (Mali & Salsbury, 2021). In EFL classrooms, digital platforms have been utilized to facilitate activities such as online discussions, collaborative writing tasks, and interactive language exercises. Technology-mediated learning environments also enable the use of multimodal learning resources that can enhance students' participation and motivation in language learning activities (Chan & Lo, 2024). However, implementing effective assessment strategies in online language learning environments remains challenging, as lecturers must carefully design assessment activities that align with learning objectives while maintaining meaningful student engagement.

Although previous studies have examined the use of digital technologies in language learning, research focusing specifically on how lecturers implement formative assessment practices in remote learning environments remains limited. Much of the existing literature has concentrated on students' perceptions of online learning or the effectiveness of particular digital platforms, while fewer studies have explored lecturers' pedagogical strategies in designing and implementing formative assessment in technology-mediated EFL classrooms. In the Indonesian higher education context, empirical research investigating remote formative assessment practices in English language learning is still relatively scarce. Therefore, examining how lecturers adapt formative assessment principles through digital technologies is important for identifying effective strategies that support students' language learning development in online environments.

Therefore, this study aims to explore how lecturers in Indonesian universities implement remote formative assessment in English language learning contexts. Specifically, this study addresses the following research questions:

1. How do Indonesian EFL lecturers implement remote formative assessment in online learning environments?

2. What digital tools and strategies are used in remote formative assessment practices?
3. How do these practices support students' language learning development?

2. Background

2.1. Formative assessment in higher education

Formative assessment is widely recognized as a crucial pedagogical approach that supports student learning in higher education. Unlike summative assessment, which evaluates final achievement, formative assessment provides continuous feedback on students' progress to inform teaching and learning adjustments (Black & Wiliam, 2009). Through ongoing monitoring and feedback, lecturers can identify learning difficulties and apply appropriate instructional strategies. Research has consistently shown that formative assessment enhances student engagement, encourages active participation, and deepens conceptual understanding (Nicol & Macfarlane-Dick, 2006; Panadero et al., 2018), while also fostering self-regulated learning as students reflect on feedback and take responsibility for their improvement.

Recent studies further highlight the role of formative assessment in promoting dialogic learning environments, where students actively participate in assessment processes. Contemporary approaches emphasize student involvement in interpreting feedback, engaging in peer evaluation, and reflecting on their learning strategies rather than relying solely on teacher-directed assessment (Boud et al., 2018). Such practices are particularly important in higher education, as they help students develop evaluative judgment skills essential for lifelong learning.

2.2. Feedback in language learning

Feedback is a central component of formative assessment, particularly in second language learning, as it provides learners with insights into their linguistic performance and guides improvements in accuracy and communicative competence (Hyland & Hyland, 2019). Effective feedback goes beyond identifying errors by offering constructive suggestions that support language development. Research shows that timely, specific, and meaningful feedback can significantly enhance students' motivation, engagement, and learning strategies, helping them recognize strengths and weaknesses and revise their work accordingly (Zhang & Hyland, 2022). Additionally, interaction between lecturers and students during feedback processes can foster dialogue that deepens understanding of language use.

Recent research has introduced the concept of feedback literacy, which refers to students' ability to understand, interpret, and effectively use feedback to improve their learning (Carless & Winstone, 2023). This perspective emphasizes that the impact of feedback depends not only on the quality of lecturers' comments but also on students' capacity to engage with and act on them (Carless & Winstone, 2023). Consequently, developing students' feedback literacy has become an important focus in higher education assessment practices.

2.3. Technology-enhanced formative assessment

The rapid advancement of digital technology has transformed assessment practices in higher education, enabling lecturers to implement technology-enhanced formative assessment through tools such as online quizzes, discussion forums, digital portfolios, and peer evaluation platforms (Bearman et al., 2020). These technologies support continuous monitoring of student learning and more efficient feedback delivery. Research indicates that digital platforms also promote participatory and collaborative learning by allowing students to engage in peer assessment and reflective discussions and receive feedback from multiple sources (Bond et al., 2021). Additionally, learning management systems and online communication tools facilitate flexible assessment practices that extend beyond traditional classroom settings (Henderson et al., 2019).

Recent studies further show that technology-enhanced formative assessment can improve student engagement and learning outcomes when aligned with effective pedagogical strategies. Digital tools enable immediate feedback and real-time tracking of learning progress, and they also support data-driven instructional decisions (Dawson et al., 2019). Consequently, technology has become a key enabler in the implementation of formative assessment in contemporary higher education.

2.4. Remote formative assessment

The growing adoption of online and hybrid learning has increased interest in remote formative assessment, which involves conducting assessment activities through digital platforms rather than in face-to-face settings. This approach enables lecturers to evaluate students' learning progress through online tasks such as digital assignments, discussion forums, and synchronous or asynchronous feedback (Hill & Barber, 2021). Studies during and after the COVID-19 pandemic highlight their importance in maintaining learning continuity as digital technologies allow lecturers to provide timely feedback, monitor engagement, and support collaboration even in fully online environments (Rapanta et al., 2020). Additionally, remote formative

assessment facilitates multimodal communication, enabling students to demonstrate language skills through text, audio, and video.

Despite the growing body of research on technology-mediated assessment, limited studies have examined how lecturers actually implement remote formative assessment in everyday teaching practices, particularly in Indonesian higher education EFL contexts. Much of the existing research focuses on technological tools or students' perspectives, rather than the practical strategies used by lecturers. Therefore, further research is needed to explore how lecturers apply remote formative assessment in real classroom settings and how these practices influence the learning process in higher education language courses.

3. Method

3.1. Research design

This study employed a qualitative case study design to explore how lecturers implement remote formative assessment in English language learning contexts. A qualitative approach was appropriate as it enabled an in-depth understanding of lecturers' experiences, perceptions, and practices in technology-mediated environments, which is essential for interpreting complex educational phenomena within real-life contexts (Creswell & Poth, 2018; Kara, 2022). Case study research further supports the investigation of contemporary phenomena in natural settings, allowing researchers to capture the complexity of educational practices within specific institutional contexts (Yin, 2018). This approach is particularly suitable for generating rich, contextualized descriptions of participants' experiences (Stake, 2020), and it provides detailed insights into the implementation of remote formative assessment in Indonesian higher education EFL classrooms.

3.2. Population and sample

The study was conducted in three public universities in Aceh Province, Indonesia: Universitas Syiah Kuala, Universitas Islam Negeri Ar-Raniry, and Universitas Samudra. These institutions were selected because they offer English language education programs and have integrated digital technologies into their teaching and learning practices. The participants were fifteen English lecturers actively teaching in the English departments of the three universities, with five lecturers recruited from each institution using purposive sampling. This sampling technique is widely applied in qualitative research to select individuals with relevant experience and knowledge related to the research focus (Saldaña, 2021). To meet the selection criteria, the participants were required to have a minimum of five years of experience teaching English at the

university level and prior involvement in online or technology-mediated instruction.

The lecturers' teaching experience ranged from five to twenty years, and they were responsible for a variety of courses, including English language skills (speaking, writing, reading, and listening), linguistics, and pedagogical subjects related to English language teaching. In terms of gender distribution, eight participants were female, and seven were male. At Universitas Syiah Kuala, the group included three female and two male lecturers; at Universitas Islam Negeri Ar-Raniry, three male and two female lecturers participated; and at Universitas Samudra, there were three female and two male lecturers. This composition ensured representation of diverse teaching experiences and perspectives across the three institutions.

3.3. Data collection

Data were collected from two primary sources: semi-structured interviews, and digital artifact analysis. The semi-structured interviews were conducted to explore lecturers' experiences and perspectives on implementing remote formative assessment in English language learning. This format enabled the researcher to use predetermined questions while allowing participants the flexibility to elaborate on their responses. Such interviews are widely used in qualitative research because they provide in-depth insights while maintaining alignment with the study's objectives (Seidman, 2019). Each interview was conducted individually, lasted approximately 15-30 minutes, and was audio-recorded with participants' consent to ensure accuracy. The recordings were then transcribed verbatim for analysis (Sutton & Austin, 2015).

In addition, digital artifacts were collected to provide supporting evidence of lecturers' remote formative assessment practices (Rapanta et al., 2020). These artifacts included online quizzes, feedback shared through learning management systems, screenshots of discussion forum interactions, and samples of students' digital assignments, with a total of thirty artifacts gathered across the three universities. The analysis focused on how lecturers designed assessment activities, delivered feedback, and monitored student learning in online environments. These materials were examined alongside the interview transcripts to identify evidence of formative assessment practices, including the use of digital tools and strategies to support learning. This process also functioned as data triangulation, helping to confirm and enrich the findings derived from the interviews (Denzin, 2017).

3.4. Data analysis

The collected data were analyzed using thematic analysis, a qualitative method for identifying, analyzing, and interpreting patterns or themes within data

(Braun & Clarke, 2006). This approach is widely used in educational research because it enables systematic organization of large datasets while supporting meaningful interpretation (Braun & Clarke, 2021). The analysis followed several stages: first, the interview transcripts and digital artifacts were reviewed to achieve familiarity with the data; second, initial codes were generated by identifying meaningful segments relevant to the research focus; third, these codes were grouped into broader categories to capture recurring patterns across participants; and finally, the categories were refined into themes representing key practices in remote formative assessment. Through this process, several major themes were identified to explain how lecturers implement remote formative assessment in English language learning contexts.

To ensure trustworthiness, the study applied the criteria of credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability (Lincoln & Guba, 1985), which are commonly used to establish rigor in qualitative research (Merriam & Tisdell, 2015). Credibility was strengthened through the use of multiple data sources, as interview data and digital artifacts were triangulated to provide a more comprehensive understanding of lecturers' practices. Transferability was addressed by offering detailed descriptions of the research context, participants, and procedures, enabling readers to assess the applicability of the findings to other contexts. Dependability was maintained through clear documentation of the research process, including data collection and analysis procedures, ensuring transparency. Confirmability was supported by grounding the findings in participants' perspectives, with interview recordings, transcripts, and digital artifacts carefully examined to ensure that the identified themes accurately reflected their experiences.

4. Results

The analysis of interview data and digital artifacts generated five major themes that describe how Indonesian EFL lecturers implement remote formative assessment in online learning environments. These themes illustrate the strategies lecturers use to adapt assessment practices to digital platforms and how such practices support students' language learning development. The themes include (1) adapting assessment tools to digital environments, (2) providing timely and constructive feedback, (3) monitoring students' learning progress, (4) facilitating collaborative learning activities, and (5) utilizing multimodal assessment tools.

4.1. Adapting assessment tools to digital learning environments

A key finding of this study is how lecturers adapted traditional assessment practices to online learning environments by transforming classroom-based

activities into digital formats. Rather than relying solely on written tests, they implemented online quizzes, discussion-based tasks, and digital assignments to capture students' learning progress. These digital platforms enabled more efficient collection and review of student work, allowing lecturers to quickly identify areas needing support, while discussion forums were used to assess participation and understanding. In general, lecturers demonstrated active efforts to redesign assessment strategies and often combined multiple platforms to support diverse formative assessment activities in remote learning contexts, as reflected in (1).

- (1) When I give them an online task or assignment, I usually use Google Classroom, WhatsApp Group, email, and sometimes I ask them to record videos, and open a discussion forum using Moodle application, and also sometimes I give them a quiz using Quizizz application. (L11)

The lecturers adopted a range of digital assessment tools for their efficiency, interactivity, and accuracy; advantages that are often difficult to achieve with conventional methods. They also emphasized the practicality of these tools in organizing assessments and managing teaching responsibilities more effectively, as reflected in (2).

- (2) Um, I, for now, prefer to use Google Forms due to my time management between teaching and other job duties. This site makes it kind of easy for me to create quizzes because I can easily set the score I need per item or question . . . (L1)

Several lecturers held structural positions and managed substantial dual workloads, making digital assessment tools a practical solution to balance teaching and administrative responsibilities while maintaining evaluation quality. Additionally, the lecturers noted that online discussion forums effectively foster critical thinking, support interactive assessment, create a more relaxed learning environment, and enable prompt, well-documented feedback.

- (3) An online discussion forum is less formal, I think. And it's quite effective to be a starting point because, based on my experience in a discussion forum, the students become more open, and they treat the Discussion Forum not like a true assessment, which is why they can write more than 200 words sometimes. But in an assignment or quiz, even though they should write more than 200 words, they write less. In the discussion forum, it is like they are posting something on their social media or in their blogs; they elaborate more. (L15)

According to the lecturer, online discussion forums foster a more relaxed and productive learning atmosphere by reducing language anxiety, promoting a supportive environment, encouraging classroom democratization, and enabling peer feedback. These findings are supported by digital artifacts, including screenshots of quizzes, discussion forums, and student submissions, which illustrate how lecturers integrated digital tools into their remote formative assessment practices, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1.

Example of Discussion Forum-Based Remote Formative Assessment

4.2. Providing Timely and Constructive Feedback

Another key finding relates to the provision of timely and constructive feedback in online learning environments. The lecturers emphasized that feedback is essential for helping students understand their learning progress and improve performance. In remote contexts, digital platforms enabled more frequent feedback compared to traditional classrooms. The lecturers reported using various channels, including learning management systems, email, and messaging applications, as well as comment features within online platforms to provide detailed suggestions. These practices allowed students to receive feedback shortly after submitting their work, supporting timely revision and improvement.

Furthermore, the lecturers highlighted that regular feedback helped sustain students' motivation and engagement during online learning. Continuous guidance enabled instructors to support learning despite physical distance,

ensuring that students remained connected to the learning process. For instance, one lecturer noted that digital quizzes allow students to receive immediate feedback:

- (4) Google Form is the most frequent platform I use for the quizzes. Because they may see instant feedback from the scores they get. (L8)

Digital quizzes provide significant benefits for both instructors and students due to their efficiency in supporting language learning. Features such as auto-grading, rapid data analysis, time efficiency, and flexible question banks simplify assessment for lecturers, while students benefit from reduced anxiety, greater independence, and continuous access to feedback for self-assessment. Additionally, the lecturers complement these tools by offering written comments to guide students in revising and improving their work, as illustrated in (5).

- (5) So, one formative assessment that I did, for example, I give responses, I give comments to the students' posts in Google Classroom, and then I send them back to the students so they can upgrade or revise their assignments. (L9)

Online written comments offer advantages over handwritten feedback, as they are clearer, easier to read, and allow students to track revision history by comparing drafts to identify recurring errors and improve future performance. In addition, some lecturers extended their feedback practices by using social media platforms such as YouTube to respond to and support students' learning.

- (6) I gave them an argumentative topic, and then I asked them to post it on their YouTube account. I give my feedback, for example, on their pronunciation, content, coherence, cohesion, and fluency in using English. L15

Many English lecturers use YouTube not only as an engaging platform but also as an effective formative assessment tool for monitoring students' speaking development. Unlike classroom presentations, recorded videos can be replayed multiple times, allowing the lecturers to provide detailed feedback on aspects such as fluency, intonation, and accuracy at specific moments. These practices illustrate how remote formative assessment leverages digital platforms to deliver timely and constructive feedback that supports continuous learning, as reflected in the YouTube-based digital artifact displayed in Figure 2.

Figure 2.

*Use of YouTube for Providing Formative Feedback***4.3. Monitoring students' learning progress**

The findings indicate that digital platforms enable lecturers to monitor students' learning progress in a more systematic way. The lecturers reported using various online tools to track participation, assignment completion, and engagement in learning activities. For instance, the lecturers reviewed students' contributions in discussion forums, monitored submissions through learning management systems, and observed progress across multiple tasks. These practices allowed them to identify students who needed additional support and adjust their instructional strategies accordingly.

In addition, continuous monitoring helped the lecturers develop a clearer understanding of students' strengths and weaknesses over time. By analyzing students' performance, they were able to provide more targeted feedback and design follow-up activities to address specific learning challenges. For example, in (7), one lecturer explained how Google Docs enabled both lecturers and students to track revisions in writing assignments:

- (7) The reason why I use Google Docs is that I can monitor the students' progress task after task... With the Google Doc, everything is recorded, the errors and the revisions. So they can remember. (L2)

Using Google Docs enabled lecturers to closely monitor students' writing processes through real-time interaction and transparent data tracking, while extensions such as Revision History or Draftback provided visual insights into students' writing behaviors, including editing frequency and duration. These features supported more detailed evaluation of learning progress, complemented by lecturers' use of learning management systems (LMS) to deliver continuous feedback, as illustrated in (8).

- (8) Throughout the class, students would be asked to complete numerous tasks and assignments, which they would later submit to our LMS. My feedback will be provided continuously and directly through the LMS or by email. (L10)

LMS reduces constraints of time and distance by enabling flexible, non-face-to-face evaluation while providing immediate scores and answer explanations for objective tasks, allowing students to quickly identify and correct mistakes. They also help the lecturers track assignment submissions and detect declining performance, enabling timely intervention through support or reminders before final assessments. These practices demonstrate how digital technologies facilitate close monitoring of learning progress and continuous academic support, as further illustrated in Figure 3 by a lecturer's use of a WhatsApp Group to provide feedback on group work.

Figure 3.

Use of WhatsApp Group for Monitoring Student Learning

4.4. Facilitating collaborative learning activities

Another important theme emerging from the data is the use of collaborative learning activities in remote formative assessment. Many lecturers encouraged students to engage in group discussions, peer review, and collaborative assignments, enabling them to exchange ideas, discuss course content, and provide feedback to one another. In practice, the lecturers organized online discussion sessions where students responded to prompts, commented on peers' contributions, and participated in academic dialogue, while peer review was commonly applied in writing tasks to support evaluation and revision. These activities not only facilitated assessment but also enhanced active learning and student engagement.

The lecturers also emphasized that collaborative tasks helped develop students' communication skills and encouraged greater responsibility in the learning process. Through peer interaction, students gained diverse perspectives and developed their understanding of course materials. For instance, one lecturer in (9) highlighted the importance of collaborative learning:

- (9) In my teaching context, when I use RFA, I also do not only focus on individual student learning but also focus on collaborative learning. (L3)

Collaborative learning in remote formative assessment is particularly effective as technology helps overcome digital isolation by providing meaningful interaction, enabling real-time peer feedback that accelerates understanding while promoting responsibility and essential digital collaboration skills. As noted by several lecturers, peer review activities also support English language development, as illustrated in (10-11) by the following lecturers' descriptions:

- (10) I also use peer reviews in a discussion forum so the students can review and give feedback on each other's work, fostering collaborative learning, and I think it is helpful for them. (L8)
- (11) I see positive aspects when using Google Classroom, for example, or Subs groups that, in one way, can engage the students to respond to their peers' questionings or their peer comments. (L9)

Peer review in online discussion forums promotes active learning by engaging students in critical evaluation of their peers' work, which extends understanding, broadens perspectives, and fosters a collaborative feedback environment while strengthening professional communication skills in digital contexts. In addition, the lecturers noted that social media platforms such as

WhatsApp facilitate peer interaction by enabling students to exchange ideas and discuss course materials more easily.

- (12) Even though some students learn by themselves from the teacher's feedback, I believe they also discuss with their friends in a WhatsApp group about their writing. (L13)

Using WhatsApp is highly beneficial as it enables fast, fluid, and inclusive communication, where lecturer feedback can spark collective discussion, allowing students to quickly clarify instructions, support one another's understanding, and engage in transparent, accessible learning via mobile devices. These findings suggest that digital platforms effectively facilitate collaborative learning and peer-supported assessment activities, as further illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4.

Online Discussion Using Zoom for Collaborative Learning

4.5. Utilizing multimodal assessment tools

The final theme highlights the use of multimodal assessment tools in remote formative assessment. The lecturers reported incorporating various forms of digital media, such as video presentations, audio recordings, and digital projects, into their assessment practices. These approaches enabled students

to demonstrate learning beyond traditional written tasks, for instance, through video submissions to assess speaking skills, audio recordings for pronunciation and listening, and multimedia projects to evaluate their ability to communicate ideas across different modes.

The lecturers noted that multimodal tasks provided broader opportunities for students to show their language abilities while also increasing engagement and participation in online learning environments. These varied formats helped sustain students' interest and supported more active assessment practices. For example, one lecturer described how students created video assignments on YouTube:

- (13) For speaking subject, I usually ask my students to make a video for homework or assignment . . . and request them to post it on YouTube. (L15)

Uploading videos to YouTube serves as both a self-reflection tool and a digital portfolio, helping students build confidence and improve pronunciation, while allowing lecturers to conduct more accurate assessments through replayable, time-specific feedback and freeing class time for interactive activities. In addition, WhatsApp was widely used for communication and assignment submission due to its accessibility, real-time multimedia support, and ability to facilitate immediate feedback and informal interaction, making it an effective medium for formative assessment.

- (14) I usually continue to give feedback to the group WhatsApp or the student's personal WhatsApp account, because you know it is faster and more interactive. We can do it at any time, in our free time. My students and I can also share documents like PPT, worksheets, voice notes, or videos. Sometimes students ask for clarification if my explanation in class was unclear. (L5)

Nearly all students and lecturers actively use WhatsApp on their mobile devices, making it highly accessible and responsive for communication. Its ability to deliver feedback in multiple formats, such as text, voice messages, and video, creates a more personal and less formal interaction, which can help reduce student anxiety when receiving corrections. Additionally, the group feature supports dynamic discussions, where feedback given to one student can benefit others, providing a collaborative and supportive learning environment. Alongside this, other lecturers, such as in (15), reported using Google Classroom to provide feedback on students' assignments:

- (15) I often employ short answer assignments, reflective reading, and a discussion board for the RFA. The platform I use when conducting those activities is Google Classroom. (L6)

Google Classroom is an effective multimodal assessment tool due to its capacity to integrate various assignment formats, such as text, video, and presentations, within a single, organized workflow. It enables lecturers to provide detailed and varied feedback through digital rubrics and direct comments, while also serving as a structured digital portfolio that documents students' language development across multiple dimensions.

The findings show that the fifteen Indonesian EFL lecturers implemented remote formative assessment through diverse pedagogical and technological strategies. By adapting assessment tools to digital platforms, providing continuous feedback, monitoring learning progress, facilitating collaborative activities, and employing multimodal assessments, the lecturers were able to effectively support students' language development and create more interactive and supportive online learning environments.

5. Discussion

This study explored how lecturers in three Indonesian universities, Syiah Kuala University, Ar-Raniry State Islamic University, and Samudra University, implemented remote formative assessment (RFA) in English language learning. The findings revealed five key strategies: adapting assessment tools to digital environments, providing timely and constructive feedback, monitoring students' learning progress, facilitating collaborative learning, and utilizing multimodal assessment tools. These strategies reveal how lecturers integrate digital technologies with formative assessment principles to support remote learning and continuous student development.

One major finding is the lecturers' ability to adapt traditional assessment practices to digital contexts. By using learning management systems, online quiz tools, and communication platforms, the lecturers redesigned rather than merely transferred assessments to online formats, leveraging digital 'affordances', à la Salmani Nodoushan (2021b), to enhance flexibility and interaction. This draws attention to the role of technology as a pedagogical mediator that supports efficient evidence collection and continuous assessment. These findings align with prior studies indicating that digital platforms can strengthen formative assessment through more interactive and flexible practices (Black & Wiliam, 2009; Bearman et al., 2020; Spector et al., 2022).

Another key aspect is the provision of timely and constructive feedback through digital communication channels, enabling the lecturers to respond

quickly to students' needs. Feedback plays a central role in formative assessment by helping learners identify gaps between current performance and expected outcomes and guiding improvement (Black & Wiliam, 2009). In language learning, such feedback is essential for developing accuracy and communicative competence through revision and practice. These practices also reflect the concept of feedback literacy, emphasizing students' ability to interpret and apply feedback effectively (Carless & Winstone, 2023).

The findings further show that RFA supports systematic monitoring of students' learning progress. Digital tools allow lecturers to track submissions, participation, and engagement over time, aligning with the formative assessment principle of using ongoing evidence to inform instruction. This continuous monitoring also promotes self-regulated learning, as students become more aware of their progress and take responsibility for improving their performance. Previous research similarly stresses the role of formative assessment in supporting reflection and adaptive learning strategies (Panadero et al., 2018).

Collaborative learning also emerged as an important component of RFA, with the lecturers incorporating peer review, group discussions, and collaborative tasks. These practices position learning as a socially mediated process, particularly valuable in language education, where interaction supports development (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021a). Through collaboration, students exchange ideas, evaluate peers' work, and deepen understanding, which enhances engagement and critical thinking (Carless & Winstone, 2023). In addition, the lecturers employed multimodal assessment tools, such as video, audio, and digital projects, allowing students to demonstrate language skills across multiple modes, thereby increasing engagement and supporting diverse learning outcomes (Spector et al., 2022).

The study also reveals several pedagogical implications. Effective RFA requires lecturers not only to use digital tools but to integrate them meaningfully into assessment design, ensuring alignment with learning objectives. Timely feedback, continuous monitoring, and interactive activities are especially important in maintaining engagement in remote settings, supporting communication, learner autonomy, and self-regulated learning. Furthermore, institutional support, such as technological infrastructure and professional development, is essential for successful implementation. The findings suggest that RFA can effectively enhance English language learning when digital technologies are strategically combined with formative assessment principles.

6. Conclusion

This study examined how Indonesian EFL lecturers implement remote formative assessment in technology-mediated learning environments. The

findings indicate that lecturers employ a range of digital tools and pedagogical strategies, including adapting traditional assessments to online platforms, providing timely and constructive feedback through various communication channels, monitoring students' progress via learning management systems, fostering collaborative learning through peer interaction, and utilizing multimodal tasks to support diverse demonstrations of language ability. These practices determine how formative assessment principles can be effectively integrated with digital technologies to promote continuous learning, enhance student engagement, and support language development by encouraging interaction, ongoing feedback, and learner autonomy. The study also emphasizes the importance of lecturers' ability to align digital tools with meaningful pedagogical objectives.

However, this study has several limitations. It involved a relatively small sample of lecturers from three universities in Aceh Province, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. In addition, the study focused primarily on lecturers' perspectives and did not explore students' experiences of remote formative assessment. Future research could address these limitations by involving a larger and more diverse sample of institutions and participants, as well as examining students' perceptions of digital formative assessment practices. Further studies may also investigate the role of institutional support, technological infrastructure, and professional development in shaping lecturers' capacity to implement effective remote formative assessment in higher education.

Authors' Statement

Yuliana and Arceli M. Amarles collaboratively contributed to the conceptualization and research design of the study. Yuliana led the data collection process, the data analysis, and the interpretation. Both authors jointly contributed to the literature review, manuscript drafting, and final editing of the manuscript.

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References

- Bearman, M., Dawson, P., Ajjawi, R., Tai, J., & Boud, D. (Eds.). (2020). *Re-imagining university assessment in a digital world*. Springer Nature.
- Black, P., & Wiliam, D. (2009). Developing the theory of formative assessment. *Educational Assessment, Evaluation and Accountability*, 21(1), 5-31. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11092-008-9068-5>
- Bond, M., Bedenlier, S., Marín, V. I., & Händel, M. (2021). Emergency remote teaching in higher education: Mapping the first global online semester. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 18(50). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-021-00282-x>
- Boud, D., Ajjawi, R., Dawson, P., & Tai, J. (2018). *Developing evaluative judgement in higher education: Assessment for knowing and producing quality work*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315109251>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77-101.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2021). *Thematic analysis: A practical guide*. Sage.
- Carless, D., & Winstone, N. (2023). Teacher feedback literacy and its interplay with student feedback literacy. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 28(1), 150-163. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13562517.2020.1782372>
- Chan, S., & Lo, N. (2024). Enhancing EFL/ESL instruction through gamification: A comprehensive review of empirical evidence. *Frontiers in Education*, 9, 1395155. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2024.1395155>
- Creswell, J. W., & Poth, C. N. (2018). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches* (4th ed.). Sage.
- Dawson, P., Henderson, M., Mahoney, P., Phillips, M., Ryan, T., Boud, D., & Molloy, E. (2019). What makes for effective feedback: staff and student perspectives. *Assessment and Evaluation in Higher Education*, 44, 1, 25-36. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2018.1467877>
- Denzin, N. K. (2017). *The research act: A theoretical introduction to sociological methods* (3rd ed.). Routledge.

- Dhawan, S. (2020). Online learning: A panacea in the time of the COVID-19 crisis. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 49(1), 5-22. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047239520934018>
- Henderson, M., Ryan, T., & Phillips, M. (2019). The challenges of feedback in higher education. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 44(8), 1237-1252. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2019.1599815>
- Heritage, M. (2010). *Formative assessment: Making it happen in the classroom*. Corwin.
- Hill, P., & Barber, M. (2021). *Preparing for a renaissance in assessment*. Pearson.
- Hyland, K., & Hyland, F. (2019). *Feedback in second language writing: Contexts and issues*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108635547>
- Kang, M., & Lam, R. (2024). Understanding university English instructors' assessment literacy: A formative assessment perspective. *Language Testing in Asia*, 14, 52. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40468-024-00323-y>
- Kara, H. (2022). *Qualitative research for quantitative researchers*. Sage.
- Lincoln, Y. S., & Guba, E. G. (1985). *Naturalistic inquiry*. Sage.
- Mali, Y. C. G., & Salsbury, T. L. (2021). Technology integration in an Indonesian EFL writing classroom. *TEFLIN Journal*, 32(2), 243-266. <https://doi.org/10.15639/http://teflinjournal.v32i2/243-266>
- Merriam, S. B., & Tisdell, E. J. (2015). *Qualitative research: A guide to design and implementation*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Nicol, D. J., & Macfarlane-Dick, D. (2006). Formative assessment and self-regulated learning: A model and seven principles of good feedback practice. *Studies in Higher Education*, 31(2), 199-218. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075070600572090>
- Nicol, D., Thomson, A., & Breslin, C. (2014). Rethinking feedback practices in higher education: A peer review perspective. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 39(1), 102-122. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2013.795518>

- Panadero, E., Andrade, H., & Brookhart, S. (2018). Fusing self-regulated learning and formative assessment: A roadmap of where we are and where we are going. *The Australian Educational Researcher*, 45, 13-31 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13384-018-0258-y>
- Pinto-Llorente, A. M., & Izquierdo-Álvarez, V. (2024). Digital learning ecosystems to enhance formative assessment in second language acquisition in higher education. *Sustainability*, 16(11), 4687. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16114687>
- Rapanta, C., Botturi, L., Goodyear, P., Guàrdia, L., & Koole, M. (2020). Online university teaching during and after the COVID-19 crisis: Refocusing teacher presence and learning activity. *Postdigital Science and Education*, 2, 923-945. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42438-020-00155-y>
- Rasmitadila, R., Aliyyah, R. R., Rachmadtullah, R., Samsudin, A., Syaodih, E., Nurtanto, M., & Tambunan, A. R. S. (2020). The perceptions of primary school teachers of online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic period: A case study in Indonesia. *Journal of Ethnic and Cultural Studies*, 7(2), 90-109. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejecs/388>
- Saldaña, J. (2021). *The coding manual for qualitative researchers* (4th ed.). Sage.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2010). The Interface between interim assessment and feedback: An opinion paper. *Journal on Educational Psychology*, 4(3), 1-8.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2021a). Language and socialization? It is all about sociosemiotics. *Rivista Italiana di Filosofia del Linguaggio*, 15(2), 209-225.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2021b). Test affordances or test function? Did we get Messick's message right? *International Journal of Language Studies*, 15(3), 127-140.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2021c). Washback or backwash? Revisiting the status quo of washback and test impact in EFL contexts. *Studies in English Language and Education*, 8(3), 869-884. <https://doi.org/10.24815/siele.v8i3.21406>
- Seidman, I. (2019). *Interviewing as qualitative research: A guide for researchers in education and the social sciences* (5th ed.). Teachers College Press.

- Selwyn, N. (2016). *Education and technology: Key issues and debates* (2nd ed.). Bloomsbury.
- Spector, J. M., Lockee, B. B., & Childress, M. D. (2022). *Learning, design, and technology: An international compendium of theory, research, practice, and policy*. Springer Nature.
- Stake, R. E. (2020). *The art of case study research*. Sage.
- Sutton, J., & Austin, Z. (2015). Qualitative Research: Data Collection, Analysis, and Management. *The Canadian Journal of Hospital Pharmacy*, 68(3), 226-231. <https://doi.org/10.4212/cjhp.v68i3.1456>
- Yin, R. K. (2018). *Case study research and applications: Design and methods* (6th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Zhang, H., Quan, J., Zhang, N., & Zhang, L. (2025). Investigating the effects of formative assessment on EFL students' achievement and motivation: A Self-Determination Theory perspective. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 16, 1664871. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2025.1664871>
- Zhang, Z., & Hyland, K. (2022). Fostering student engagement with feedback: An integrated approach. *Assessing Writing*, 51, 100586. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asw.2021.100586>